

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**A Case Report****STUDY ABOUT YOUNG GIRL SUFFERING FROM REPEATED
PITYRIASIS LICHENOIDES CHRONICA AND LICHEN
STRIATUS****¹Dr. Abdul Sami, ²Dr. Syed Zain Hasan Zaidi, ³Hafiz Muhammad Nouman Ali**¹DHQ, Faisalabad²Shaikh Khalifa Bin Zayed Al-Nahyan Medical and Dental College³Sheikh Zayed Medical College Rahim Yar Khan**Abstract:**

This research study is about young girl whose age was 11 years. She was suffering with repeated pityriasis lichenoides chronica and lichen striatus. She was not found with such association in history. There is uncertainty that whether this relationship is accidental or due to some reasons. However, involvement of some pathway that is common in both disorders was observed. Lichen striatus is usually found in children and is an un-frequent condition. Next to Blaschko's lines, the abrasions have a straight dispersal. Pityriasis lichenoides is an un-frequent gentle disease of skin. There are two alternatives of this disorder i.e chronic and acute.

Keywords: Infection, Lichen striatus, Pityriasis lichenoides chronica.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Abdul Sami,**
DHQ, Faisalabad

QR code

Please cite this article in press Abdul Sami et al., Study about Young Girl Suffering From Repeated Pityriasis Lichenoides Chronica and Lichen Striatus., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

This disorder of unknown reasons called lichen striatus, is a restricted, swelling dermatosis. This disorder is mostly found in children with the age limit between 5 to 15 years [1]. It seems like a plan – topped erythematous papules, scaly in appearance. These papules are grouped together in regular or irregular pattern like the Blaschko's lines. These abrasions are usually observed on branches and are unique. This disorder starts at once. Advancement of disease is in days and weeks. Hypopigmentation may remain within months to ever years, after the swelling [2, 3]. Somatic mosaicism is illustrated by Blaschko's lines. It indicates that during progression, clumps of unusual keratinocytes are dispersed. It is believed that both environmental and genetic factor contribute to LS. However, exact reasons are still uncertain.

The disorder of Pityriasis lichenoides (PL) is not very frequently occurring. It has two alternatives: chronic PL (PLC) and acute PL (Pityriasis lichenoides et varioliformis acuta [PLEVA]). PLC and PLEVA are not two different disorder but they form the polar ends of clinicopathological spectrum. PLC has no necrotic abrasions. It appears as little, scaly papules. Whereas, PLEVA may have ulcerative, Haemorrhagic and necrotic variations. [4].

The existence of exact pathway of PLC is not reported get. But there are conceivable theories that explains pathogenesis of PLC. According to one of them, there is indication of inflammatory reaction of disorder as a result of an immune complex mediated

hypersensitivity vasculitis or an infectious agent. The inflammatory response is noticed by the disorder to an underlying T – cell dyscrasias. This is indicated by the presence of monoclonal T-cell in majority of cases of PLEVA and few cases of PLC [5]. In this study, young girl is examined who was suffering from repeated PLS and LS.

CASE REPORT:

This study was about a young girl whose age was II years. She was suffering with pruritic, linear erythematous popular eruption on the right arm. The relation of erythematous papules with overlying scale on the trunk of was observed with this disease. The girl was suffering with disease for about 56 days. (Figures 1a, 1b). Next to lines of Blaschko, the abrasion of arm was observed. The girl had varicella infection approximately 3 weeks prior to illustration of dermatoses. NO medical issue or atopy was observed in the girl. She was also not using medications. On the trunk, same hypopigmented scars was observed at time of examination and these scars were dispersed.

There were indications of diffuse lysis of the basal layer, scattered melanin incontinence, exocytosis, lymphocytic infiltrate around hair follicle, epidermal hyperkeratosis, band like lymphocytic infiltration of dermis and focal parakeratosis, from arm. There found no interference of nail and mucosal abrasions. Arranged in straight pattern, erythematous papules were found in right arm of girl. These papules were next to Blaschko's lines. (Figure -2a)

Figure-1a: Linear erythematous papule eruption along the Blaschko line on the right arm. |Figure-1b: Papulosquamous eruption on the trunk.

The girl was detected with LS, when examined histologically and clinically. From the trunk, a second skin biopsy was taken in upper dermis, parakeratosis, hyperkeratosis, and erythrocyte extravasation were indicated through this biopsy. (Figure-2b).

Figure-2a

- 1) Hyperkeratosis, focal parakeratosis, perivascular lymphocytes infiltrate in the dermis (Hematoxylin and eosin stain X200).
- 2) Lymphocytes infiltrate around the hair follicle (Hematoxylin and eosin stain X 400).

Figure-2b

Focal parakeratosis and perivascular lymphocytic infiltration in the upper dermis (Hematoxylin and eosin stain X 400).

Small Image: Basal vacuolar degeneration (Hematoxylin and eosin stain X1000).

As compare to PLC, this situation was similar. By using topical corticosteroids, the girl was treated. The abrasions on the arm of the girls were vanished. Just slight hypopigmentation was left an arm after the two months treatment. On the other hand, there was no complete removal of abrasions from the trunk.

DISCUSSION:

The case which is discussed in the present study, is the first case that is found in repeated LS and PLS. The factors contributing to LS are still uncertain. Its incidence has been noticed in atopic patients and siblings. The people with immunization or infections are also observed with this disorder [6, 7]. The agents of infection like viruses, may contribute to this disease. It is due to the fact that this disorder is dominant in particular reasons most commonly in summer and spring as indicated by many studies [8, 9]. It is considered that LS begins after 10 days of tonsillitis and after 10 days of flu like illness in pair of siblings. In both siblings, incidence of was reported at same time. This indicate that there exists a common agent (e.g. viral infection) that contribute to this disorder. In one case of LS, the presence of varicella infection was reported according to one study [10].

There exists uncertainty about reasons of PL. But there is possibility of various factors. These factors include parvovirus B19, these viruses (cytomegalovirus [CMV], Epstein – Barr Virus, varicella lobster virus [VLV]), proliferation of lymphocytes due to infectious agent, human immunodeficiency virus [HIV], bacterial infections and associations with *Toxoplasma gondii*. The disorder is activated by the infections. This hypothesis is supported by the fact that start of disorder with streptococcal pharyngitis, *T. gondii* and infections of upper is respiratory track and prevalence of disorder in fall or winter. Despite of fact that onset of PL is usually in fall or winter, 30% patients were observed with viral infection PL, according to one study [11]. The present study supports the hypothesis that both disorders are caused by on infective agents.

CONCLUSION:

This study reported the presence of both disorder LS and PL in our case, who was suffering with varicella infection. This infection may contribute to both of these disorders. Many such cases and research studies are required for more knowledge.

REFERENCES:

1. Ersoy-Evans S, Greco MF, Mancini AJ, Subasi N, Paller AS. Pityriasis lichenoides in childhood: A retrospective review of 124 patients. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2007; 56:205-10.
2. Tilly JJ, Drolet BA, Esterly NB. Lichenoid eruptions in children. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2004; 51: 606-24.
3. Weinberg JM, Kristal L, Chooback L, Honig PJ, Kramer M, Lessin SR. The clonal nature of pityriasis lichenoides. *Arch Dermatol.* 2002; 138:1063-7.
4. Peramiqel L, Baselga E, Dalmau J, Roe E, del Mar Campus M, Alomar A. Lichen striatus: clinical and epidemiological review of 23 cases. *Eur J Pediatr.* 2006;165: 267-9.
5. Bowers S, Warshaw EM. Pityriasis lichenoides and its subtypes. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 2006;55: 557-72.
6. Abagge KT, Marinoni LP, Giraldo S, Carvalho VO, Santini CO, Favre H. Lichen striatus: Description of 89 cases in children. *Pediatr Dermatol.* 2004; 21: 440-3.
7. Patrizi A, Neri I, Fiorentini C, Bonci A, Ricci G. Lichen striatus: clinical and laboratory features of 115 children. *Pediatr Dermatol.* 2004; 21: 197-204.
8. Patrizi A, Neri I, Fiorentini C, Chiericato C, Bonci A. Simultaneous occurrence of lichen striatus in siblings. *Pediatr Dermatol.* 1997;14:293-5.
9. Hafner C, Landthaler M, Vogt T. Lichen striatus (blaschkitis) following varicella infection. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol.* 2006; 20: 1345-7.
10. Kennedy D, Rogers M. Lichen striatus. *Pediatr Dermatol.* 1996; 13: 95-9.
11. Dragos V, Mervic L, Zgavec B. Lichen striatus in a child after immunization. A case report. *Acta Dermatovenerol Alp Pannonica Adriat.* 2006; 15: 178-80.